

Modernization of the Brazilian Free Energy Market: Analysis of the Progressive Liberalization Process and Its Regulatory Impacts

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Abstract—The liberalization process of the Brazilian electricity sector has consolidated over the past two decades, culminating in the full opening of the Free Energy Market to high-voltage consumers as of January 2024. This article analyzes the regulatory, institutional, and operational foundations of this transformation, based on qualitative research of an exploratory and descriptive nature, grounded in document analysis and a systematic literature review. The main regulatory milestones were examined, ranging from Law No. 10,848/2004 to Provisional Measure No. 1,304/2025, as well as recent operational data from the Electric Energy Trading Chamber referring to the first two years of expanded access to the Free Contracting Environment. The results indicate that the Brazilian model is characterized as a hybrid structure, combining tariff regulation mechanisms and free contractual negotiation, with progressive and institutionally structured liberalization. There is evidence of significant growth in the number of participating agents, an increase in traded volume, and reported tariff savings for migrating consumers. The analysis also identifies regulatory challenges associated with future expansion to low-voltage consumers, including the need for consumer protection mechanisms and improved regulatory oversight. It is concluded that the modernization of the Brazilian free energy market is aligned with international liberalization trends, presenting promising preliminary results, although continuous monitoring is required to ensure competitive balance and systemic protection.

Index Terms—Free Energy Market; Electricity Sector Liberalization; Energy Regulation; ANEEL; Energy Trading.

I. INTRODUCTION

The liberalization of electricity markets constitutes a global trend observed since the pioneering reforms implemented in the United Kingdom during the 1980s, subsequently expanding to several European, Latin American, and Asian countries (Joskow, 2008; Pollitt, 2012). According to Joskow (2008), the restructuring of electricity markets seeks to promote competition, economic efficiency, and cost reduction through the separation of regulated activities, such as transmission and distribution, from competitive activities, such as energy generation and trading. In the Brazilian context, this process intensified following the enactment of Law No. 10,848/2004, whose developments have been observable since the full market opening to high-voltage consumers in January 2024.

The Brazilian Free Energy Market represents a contracting environment in which consumers freely negotiate price, term, volume, and payment terms with suppliers, distinguishing itself from the Regulated Contracting Environment, where distributors acquire energy through regulated auctions. According to Pinto Junior et al. (2007), this duality characterizes the Brazilian hybrid model, which combines elements of competitive markets with tariff regulation mechanisms. The Electric Energy Trading Chamber plays a central role in this system, being responsible for operationalizing transactions, registering contracts, and settling differences between contracted and consumed volumes (Brasil, 2004a).

Recent studies have demonstrated that the progressive liberalization of electricity markets can generate notable benefits, including price reductions, technological innovation, and greater diversification of the energy matrix (Pollitt, 2012). Pollitt (2012) argues that competitive markets incentivize investments in operational efficiency and renewable energy sources. In Brazil, the opening to all high-voltage consumers initiated two years ago represents a significant structural transformation, already affecting thousands of consumer units and moving billions of reais in new energy transactions (CCEE, 2025a). The accumulated experience provides important insights for evaluating the next stages of liberalization, scheduled to reach low-voltage commercial and industrial consumers in 2027 and, subsequently, the residential segment, following the timeline established by the Ministry of Mines and Energy (Brasil, 2022b). The relevance of this research is justified by the need to understand the regulatory, economic, and operational implications of one of the most significant reforms in the Brazilian electricity sector since its initial restructuring, considering the lessons learned from the first years of implementation, as highlighted by studies on energy transitions in emerging markets (Bhattacharyya, 2011; Pollitt, 2012).

II. METHODOLOGY

The present research is characterized as a qualitative study of exploratory and descriptive nature, grounded in documen-

tary analysis and systematic review of specialized literature. The collection of primary data focused on official documents published by regulatory bodies and sectoral legislation between 2004 and 2026, including operational data from the CCEE relating to the first two years of full market opening to high-voltage consumers. The documentary corpus included Law No. 10,848/2004, Decree No. 5,163/2004, MME Ordinance No. 50/2022, ANEEL Normative Resolution No. 1,000/2021, Law No. 14,300/2022, and Provisional Measure No. 1,304/2025, as well as technical documents from the CCEE, ANEEL, and MME.

The bibliographic review followed a systematic protocol based on Tranfield et al. (2003), encompassing national and international literature on electricity market liberalization. The databases consulted included Web of Science, Scopus, Scielo, and Google Scholar, with descriptors such as *electricity market liberalization*, *energy sector reform*, and *power market deregulation*, prioritizing publications between 2000 and 2026.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the regulatory milestones of the Brazilian Free Energy Market reveals an evolutionary trajectory characterized by progressive liberalization over more than two decades. The model established by Law No. 10,848/2004 instituted a fundamental dichotomy between the Regulated Contracting Environment and the Free Contracting Environment, creating a structure that Bhattacharyya (2011) classifies as a hybrid market, in which elements of tariff regulation and free negotiation coexist. This institutional architecture reflects a deliberate choice by the Brazilian regulator to promote a gradual transition, distinguishing itself from more radical reforms implemented in countries such as England, which privatized and liberalized its electricity sector abruptly between 1989 and 1990 under the Thatcher government (Newbery, 2006; Pollitt, 2012), and Chile, a world pioneer in electricity sector deregulation in 1982 through the Electric Services Law, which implemented large-scale vertical disintegration and privatization (Fischer et al., 2003).

The creation of the Electric Energy Trading Chamber by Decree No. 10,848/2004 represented a relevant institutional innovation. According to Hunt (2002), the existence of an independent market operator constitutes an essential element for the efficient functioning of liberalized electricity systems, ensuring transparency and security in transactions. The CCEE has played a fundamental role in market stabilization, processing billions of reais in annual transactions while maintaining a relatively low default rate. Operational data from 2024 and 2025 indicate an expressive increase in the volume of energy traded in the free environment, reflecting the expansion permitted by MME Ordinance No. 50/2022 (Brasil, 2022b).

MME Ordinance No. 50/2022 marked a decisive turning point by allowing all Group A consumers to migrate to the free market from January 2024 onwards, regardless of their contracted demand. This measure expanded the universe of market participants. Meeus et al. (2005) demonstrate that the reduction of entry barriers constitutes an effective strategy

for the development of competition. The first two years in Brazil confirm this trend, with 25,966 new consumer units in 2024, representing growth of 67%, and 18,300 additional migrations from January to September 2025, according to data from CCEE (2025b) and ABRACEEL (2025).

ANEEL Normative Resolution No. 1,000/2021 consolidated the regulatory framework for energy trading, establishing streamlined migration procedures and reducing bureaucratic requirements (Brasil, 2021). The simplification implemented in July 2024 has been identified as an essential factor in the success of market expansion, enabling smaller consumers to access the benefits of free contracting with the assistance of specialized traders. The institution of the Supplier of Last Resort represents an innovative risk mitigation mechanism, guaranteeing temporary supply to consumers that may become uncontracted. This safeguard addresses the concern identified by Joskow (2006) regarding vulnerable consumers in liberalized markets. The Californian experience documented by Borenstein (2002), marked by blackouts and price manipulation, reinforces the importance of adequate protection mechanisms.

Law No. 14,300/2022, which regulates distributed generation, intersects relevantly with liberalization, creating opportunities for hybrid models (Brasil, 2022a). Lopes et al. (2016) highlight that the convergence between liberalization and distributed generation enhances systemic innovation. The German experience analyzed by Morris and Pehnt (2014) demonstrates how integrated policies can accelerate the energy transition. Provisional Measure No. 1,304/2025 introduces additional directives with emphasis on energy storage and energy efficiency, aligning with trends identified by IEA (2021). Gillingham et al. (2009) argue that combining liberalization with efficiency policies can generate important synergies, since consumers with greater control over energy choices tend to invest more in efficiency technologies.

Significant challenges remain for the next stages, particularly the expansion to low-voltage consumers in 2027. Littlechild (2006) and Defeuilley (2009) identify specific risks when liberalization reaches residential consumers, including informational asymmetry, difficulties in comparing offers, and abusive commercial practices. The Brazilian regulatory design will need to incorporate adequate safeguards, consumer education mechanisms, and rigorous enforcement to mitigate these risks.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The modernization process of the Brazilian Free Energy Market represents a structural transformation in the national electricity sector. The initial results since the market opening to high-voltage consumers in 2024 suggest potential for efficiency gains, cost reductions, and sectoral innovation. The regulatory trajectory demonstrates that Brazil has opted for a model of progressive liberalization, distinguishing itself from more radical reforms, which has allowed for incremental adjustments and mitigation of systemic risks. The legal milestones from Law No. 10,848/2004 to Provisional Measure

No. 1,304/2025 have built a robust institutional framework, grounded in international experiences and adapted to the Brazilian context (Brasil, 2004b, 2025).

The analysis of preliminary results indicates encouraging trends, with new consumers joining the free environment, growth in volumes traded by the CCEE, and tariff savings across various segments. Competition among energy traders has intensified, generating diversification of offerings. These developments align with predictions from the international literature on electricity market liberalization (Bhattacharyya, 2011; Joskow, 2008; Pollitt, 2012). Significant challenges remain for the next stages, particularly the expansion to low-voltage consumers. Brazil will need to develop information programs, strengthen enforcement, and ensure that social protection instruments remain effective. The integration between liberalization and energy transition policies emerges as a strategic opportunity (IEA, 2021; Morris and Pehnt, 2014). It is concluded that the modernization of the Brazilian electricity sector demonstrates alignment with international trends and presents promising preliminary results.

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